

Evaluation of Diabetic Nephroprotective Potential of *Acacia pennata* (L.)

Wild Extract in Streptozotocin induced Diabetic rats

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Abstract:

Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is a major micro vascular complication of diabetes, leading to progressive renal failure and end-stage renal disease. The present study evaluated the nephroprotective efficacy of *Acacia pennata* (L.) Willd ethanolic leaf extract (APLE) in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic nephropathy in rats. The Fresh leaves of *A. pennata* were extracted with 60% ethanol by cold maceration. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of flavonoids, phenols, alkaloids, tannins, steroids, and glycosides, and acute toxicity testing (OECD guideline 423) revealed no toxicity up to 2000 mg/kg. Diabetes was induced using STZ (45 mg/kg *i.p.*), and animals were divided into five groups: normal control, diabetic control, standard (Metformin 200 mg/kg *p.o.*), and two test groups treated with APLE (200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg *p.o.*) for 8 weeks. Biochemical parameters such as fasting blood glucose, lipid profile, serum creatinine, urea, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), albumin, urinary protein, and antioxidant enzyme levels (SOD, CAT, GSH, MDA) were evaluated, along with pancreas and renal histopathology. APLE treatment significantly reduced hyperglycemia, improved lipid metabolism, restored renal function markers, and enhanced antioxidant enzyme levels while reducing lipid peroxidation. Histological examination revealed preserved glomerular structure, reduced mesangial expansion, and near-normal renal histoarchitecture in treated rats. The nephroprotective effects of APLE are attributed to its flavonoid and phenolic content conferring antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-hyperglycemic activities. In conclusion, *A. pennata* ethanolic leaf extract exhibits significant protective effects against STZ-induced diabetic nephropathy, supporting its potential as a natural therapeutic alternative for diabetic renal complications.

Keywords: *Acacia pennata*; Antioxidant; Diabetic nephropathy; Flavonoids; Nephroprotection; Streptozotocin

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both [1]. The disease is associated with serious microvascular and macrovascular complications, including retinopathy, neuropathy, cardiovascular disease, and nephropathy, which contribute significantly to morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs [2]. Diabetic nephropathy (DN) is one of the most severe and progressive microvascular complications of diabetes, ultimately leading to end-stage renal disease (ESRD). DN affects nearly 30–40% of diabetic patients and represents the leading cause of chronic kidney disease worldwide [3, 4].

The diabetic hyperglycemia accelerates non-enzymatic glycation, leading to advanced glycation end-products (AGEs) that trigger inflammation, oxidative stress, and renal fibrosis. Activation of cytokines, chemokines, and NF- κ B signaling contributes to mesangial cell proliferation and extracellular matrix deposition [5]. Hyperfiltration and activation of the renin–angiotensin system exacerbate renal injury. These complex mechanisms ultimately compromise renal function and accelerate nephron loss [6].

Conventional management of DN primarily involves strict glycemic control, antihypertensive agents (especially renin–angiotensin system inhibitors), and lifestyle modifications. While these measures slow disease progression, they often fail to halt or reverse renal damage. Hence, there is a need to identify safer, cost-effective, and multitargeted therapeutic agents, particularly from natural sources, to prevent and manage diabetic nephropathy [3, 7]. Plants rich in flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and alkaloids exhibit significant antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antihyperglycemic activities [8, 9].

Acacia pennata (L.)Willd, commonly known as climbing wattle or “Agnijhara” in traditional medicine, belongs to the family Fabaceae. It is a perennial shrub widely distributed in South and Southeast Asia. Traditionally, different parts of the plant have been used for the treatment of inflammation, fever, skin diseases, intestinal infections, and liver disorders. The leaves and

tender shoots are consumed as vegetables in several Asian communities, reflecting its nutritional as well as medicinal importance [10].

The presence of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, and terpenoids in the *A. pennata* are associated with diverse pharmacological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, and anti-diabetic effects. However, limited scientific studies have specifically investigated its potential in renal protection, particularly in the context of diabetic nephropathy [10, 11]. Therefore, this study aimed to investigating the ethanolic leaves extract of *A. pennata* in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic rats provides a scientific basis to validate its nephroprotective efficacy.

Materials and Methods

Collection and authentication of *Acacia pennata*

The leaves of *A. pennata* were collected from different geographical locations of Erode and Coimbatore districts, Tamil Nadu. It was collected during the months of January - February 2025. Then the collected plant material was botanically identified and authenticated by The Joint Director, Botanical Survey of India, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India (Specimen Ref. no.: 07/2025).

Preparation and Extraction of *Acacia pennata*

The collected fresh plant materials were thoroughly cleaned and the separated leaves were shade dried until completely dried. The dried materials were then coarsely powdered by a mechanical grinding and sieved (Mesh no. 40). The powdered materials were initially defatted with petroleum ether (40-60°C) and then extracted with 70% v/v ethanol, by continuous hot percolation techniques using soxhelt apparatus until the siphon tube clear. After completion of the extraction, it was filtered and dried at 60°C in rotary evaporator to produce a semisolid mass. The dried extract was stored at 4°C in an air tight container until further use.

Preliminary phytochemical analysis

The *A. pennata* ethanolic leaf extract (APLE) was subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis for identifying the phyto constituents present in the extract. The tests were carried out by standard procedures [12].

Quantitative analysis

Estimation of total alkaloid content

To determine the total alkaloid content in the *A.pennata* leaves ethanolic extract (APLE) was dissolved with 1ml of 2N Hcl and filtered. The filtered solution was transferred into the separating funnel, and then 5 ml of phosphate buffer and 5 ml bromocresol green solution (BCG) were added. Then this mixer was diluted with chloroform. The absorbance of the test and standard solutions were determined at 470 nm. Atropine 20-100 µg/ml was used as standard. The total alkaloid content was expressed as mg of Atropine (AE)/g of extract [13].

Estimation of total flavonoid content

Total flavonoid content in the APLE was estimated by AlCl₃ method. Quercetin was used as standard. The quercetin 1 mg/ml methanolic solution was prepared and different aliquots 20-100µg/ml from this solution was prepared with methanol. 3 ml of APLE solution (1mg/ml solution in methanol) or standard solution was added into the test tube containing 1 ml of 2% AlCl₃ methanolic solution and allowed to stand for 1 hour at room temperature. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 420 nm. The total flavonoid content was expressed as mg of Quercetin (QE)/g of the extract [14].

Estimation of total phenolic content

The total phenolic content in the APLE was determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu method with slight modification. The 0.1 ml of extract was treated with 0.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 1.5 ml of 7% sodium carbonate. The combined solution was shaken well and made up to 10 ml with distilled water. Then it was incubated in dark at room temperature for 2 hrs. Then the absorbance of the test and standard was taken at 725 nm in spectrometer against a reagent blank. Gallic acid (20-100 µg/ml) was used as standard. The total phenolic content was expressed as mg of gallic acid (GAE)/gm of extract [15].

Acute oral Toxicity Studies

Acute oral toxicity of *A. pennata* leaves ethanolic extract (APLE) was evaluated as per OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) test guideline 423 [16]. Three female rats were treated with a single oral dose of APLE 2000 mg/kg. After administration, each animal was individually observed for the clinical sign, symptoms and occurrence of mortality for the first 30 minutes, followed by special attention for the first 4 hours and periodically for 24 hours, thereafter daily for 14 days.

Experimental animals

The colony inbred albino wistar rats (200-230g) were obtained from Central Animal house of Sri Abirami College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore. The animals were kept under standard environmental conditions of 12/12 light/dark rhythm, maintained under controlled room temperature ($23\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) and a relative humidity of $60\pm 10\%$, in polypropylene cages. They were fed with standard pellet diet and water ad libitum. The animals were acclimatized under laboratory conditions seven days prior to initiation of the experiment.

The experimental protocol was carried out according to the guidelines of the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), India and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of Sri Abirami College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore; Care and use of laboratory animals were confirmed to CCSEA guidelines. (IAEC Reference No: SACOP/Re/M. Pharm/03/2025 Dated: 21.06.2025)

Induction of diabetic nephropathy (STZ induced)

Diabetes was induced by a single injection of streptozotocin (STZ, 45 mg/kg, i.p. freshly prepared in 0.1 M citrate ice cold buffer pH 4.5) in rats. The control group received equal volume of vehicle (0.1 M citrate ice cold buffer, pH 4.5). Initial blood glucose level was measured from tail vein using glucose meter (ACCU-CHEK). The induction of diabetes mellitus was confirmed by measuring blood glucose levels after 72 hrs. The rats with fasting blood glucose level (FBG) > 250 mg/dL were considered as diabetic rats and included in further studies.

Experimental Design

The thirty animals were divided into five groups of six each. After induction of diabetes, group-I served as normal control receives 0.5% CMC (1 ml/kg *p.o.*), group II- V was induced with diabetic control, group-III-V served as treatment groups received metformin 100 mg/kg, APLE 200 mg/kg & 400 mg/kg body weight respectively for 8 weeks.

Measurement of blood glucose level and body weight changes

The fasting blood glucose levels were measured before treatment and on 1st, 2nd, 4th, 6th & 8th weeks respectively. Through tail vein blood sampling using a single touch glucometer (ACCU-CHECK, Active, Roche diabetic Care GmbH, Germany). The changes in body weight of each

animal were determined at the initiation and weekly up to 8 weeks by using standard weighing balance.

Serum Biochemical Analysis

On the completion of 8 weeks, blood sample was withdrawn via retro orbital plexus. Collected blood samples were centrifuged at 1300xg for 10 minutes to separation of serum and stored at -20^o C until assay. The serum lipid profile like low-density lipoprotein (LDL), total cholesterol (TC), high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, and triglyceride (TG) were analyzed by using the semi-auto analyzer kits techniques following the manufacturer's instruction (ARKRAY Healthcare Pvt. Ltd., Surat, India). The kits code are LDL cholesterol (71LS400-56), HDL cholesterol (71LS300-56), and for triglyceride (72LS100-60). The serum albumin, Creatinine & blood urea nitrogen (BUN) were analyzed by using established kit procedures and automated VITROS 5.0/F auto analyzer.

Urine parameters

A metabolic cage was used to collect the 24-hour urine samples for the determination of urine creatinine, albumin and total protein by using established kit procedures and automated VITROS 5.0/F auto analyzer.

Kidney Fractional Weight

At the end of the study on day 57 animals were euthanized with a high dosage of anesthesia and kidneys were isolated, washed, blotted in filter paper, weighed, and calculated with the below formula,

$$Kidney\ Fractional\ Weight = \frac{Kidney\ weigh(g)x^2}{Total\ body\ weight\ (g)} \times 100$$

Kidney tissue antioxidant assay

One small section of right kidney was harvested from the rats and precisely weighed. Subsequently, isotonic saline was added according to the tissue weight: Saline volume=1:9 (w/v). Following homogenization at 4°C by an electric homogenate, the homogenates were centrifuged at 1,100xg for 15 min at room temperature. The kidney homogenate supernatant was

used for estimate the kidney antioxidant parameters. SOD activity, MDA content, GSH Px and catalase levels were measured using commercially available kits, according to manufacturer's protocol.

Histopathological examination

At the end of study on day 57, the pancreas and left kidney tissue was isolated from each rats and fixed in 10% neutral formal saline, dehydrated with the increasing concentration of ethanol, and after that immersed in xylene and embedded in paraffin wax. The blocks were longitudinally sectioned at 5 μ m thickness from the center. The section was mounted on a slide and stained by the hematoxylin and eosin (HE) staining procedure. The stained sections were examined under a light microscope with 40 X magnification for histopathological changes.

Statistical analysis

The data were statistical analyzed by using GraphPad software (Prism 8.0; GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). All data were expressed in mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The groups of data were compared with analysis repeated measures ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparison post-hoc tests. The values of $P < 0.05$ were considered as a statistical significant difference.

Results

Extraction Value

The *Acacia pennata* ethanolic leaves extract (APLE) cumulative extraction value was calculated as 23.26% w/w yield percentage.

Qualitative Phytochemical Analysis

The result of primary phytochemical screening of *Acacia pennata* ethanolic leaves extract showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, steroids, glycosides, proteins, tannins, phenols, terpens & sterols.

Quantitative Phytochemical Estimation

The major phytoconstituents alkaloids, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds total content in the *A. pennata ethanolic* extract is mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Quantitative Phytochemical Estimation of *A. pennata* ethanolic extract

S. No.	Phytoconstituents	Quantity (mg/g)
1.	Total alkaloid content	23.35 ± 2.35
2.	Total flavonoid content	52.15 ± 3.09
3.	Total phenolic content	45.00 ± 2.43

N=3, values are expressed as mean ± SEM.

Acute oral toxicity study

The acute oral toxicity results of *A. pennata ethanolic* leaves extract at the limited dose of 2000 mg/kg single dosing revealed that normal weight gain in the treated animals. There were also no toxic symptoms, mortality, observational, behavioral and somatomotor changes observed after single dosing of APLE. These results indicate that the APLE was found to safer for acute use at the tested dose level of 2000 mg/kg. Hence the lethal dose of 50% (LD50) of *A. pennata ethanolic* extract is greater than 2000 mg/kg. Hence, based on the body surface factor 1/10th of the tested maximum (2000 mg/kg) acute oral toxicity dose of 200 mg/kg was selected as the low dose, twofold higher than the low dose 400 mg/kg was selected as the high dose for further *in vivo* studies.

Effect of *A. pennata ethanolic* leaves extract on blood glucose level of STZ- diabetic rats

Administration of STZ led to significant (P<0.001) increase in fasting blood glucose levels in the diabetic group as compared to the normal control group, it was gradually increased throughout 8 weeks after induction. Furthermore, STZ-diabetic rats treated with Metformin, APLE 200 mg/kg & 400 mg/kg MPGL demonstrated decrease in the fasting blood glucose levels at the end of 8 weeks. The significant hypoglycemic effect of APLE was observed after 4 week of treatments, whereas STZ-diabetic rats treated with 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg APLE showed a more significant (P<0.001) decrease in the fasting blood glucose levels at the end of 8 weeks (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on blood glucose level of STZ- diabetic rats

Treatment	Fasting Blood glucose levels (mg/dL)						
	Baseline	After Induction	1 st Week	2 nd Week	4 th week	6 th week	8 th week
Group-I (Normal Control)	102.25±12.3 3	104.54±7.54	103.43±6.25	102.43±5.64	107.32±4.54	102.00±3.56	107.34±6.87
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	103.43±8.34	296.43±11.35 ^c	325.54±8.44 ^c	340.32±3.46 ^c	367.98±5.43 ^c	420.27±6.56 ^c	432.43±7.54 ^c
Group-III (Metformin - 200 mg/kg)	104.27±9.25	287.56±10.43 ^c	287.67±9.87 ^c	263.23±6.30 ^c	257.54±6.33 ^c ^e	212.37±3.64 ^c ^f	197.23±11.20 ^f
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	102.65±6.75	289.23±8.76 ^c	290.43±7.43 ^c	288.47±5.23 ^c	276.32±9.21 ^c ^d	257.27±6.78 ^c ^f	226.25±13.20 ^b ^f
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	103.54±3.45	297.35±7.85 ^c	300.34±2.45 ^c	287.35±3.67 ^c	256.34±7.45 ^c ^e	224.09±7.54 ^c ^f	189.12±10.24 ^f

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^dP<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on changes in body weight of STZ diabetic rats

At the end of study on day 57 the STZ induced diabetic rats showed significant ($P<0.001$) reduction in body weight gain than the normal control. The treatment with Metformin, APLE 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg improve the body weight in STZ induced diabetic rats. In comparison between the treatments APLE 400 mg/kg showed significant ($P<0.01$) weight improvement in diabetic rats (Table 3).

Table 3: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on changes in body weight of STZ diabetic rats

Treatment	Initial body weight (g)	Final body weight (g)
Group-I (Normal Control)	225.45±10.54	302.27±9.23
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	229.34±7.67	219.82±5.43 ^c
Group-III (Metformin -200 mg/kg)	234.27±8.97	244.67±6.46 ^{cd}
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	227.29±6.35	234.54±3.43 ^c
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	233.32±7.52	256.43±3.42 ^{bc}

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^a $P<0.05$; ^b $P<0.01$; ^c $P<0.001$ Vs Group I. ^d $P<0.05$; ^e $P<0.01$; ^f $P<0.001$ Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on serum lipid profile of STZ diabetic rats

Diabetic dyslipidemia was successfully established in rats, as indicated by significant ($P < 0.01$) increased LDL-c, TG and TC levels, and decreased HDL-c levels in diabetic rats as compared to the normal control. The treatment of Metformin, APLE 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg counteracted the above mentioned alterations in diabetic rats; serum LDL-c, TG and TC were reduced and HDL-c was increased. In comparison between the treatments APLE -400 mg/kg showed significant decreases blood lipids in T2DN rats (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on serum lipid profile of STZ diabetic rats

Treatment	TC (mg/dl)	TG (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)
Group-I (Normal Control)	155.88 ± 5.43	78.12 ± 1.44	36.04 ± 2.33	104.22 ± 7.23
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	188.58 ± 2.45 ^c	149.22 ± 3.56 ^c	22.31 ± 3.87 ^c	136.43 ± 3.49 ^a
Group-III (Metformin -200 mg/kg)	171.97 ± 7.32 ^b	127.30 ± 4.32 ^c	29.27 ± 4.09 ^b	117.24 ± 9.86 ^d
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	161.07 ± 5.78 ^d	109.27 ± 1.09 ^{bd}	32.25 ± 2.08 ^c	106.97 ± 5.37 ^d
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	147.17 ± 7.33 ^c	97.65 ± 3.20 ^{af}	35.00 ± 4.33 ^f	92.64 ± 7.65 ^e

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^a $P < 0.05$; ^b $P < 0.01$; ^c $P < 0.001$ Vs Group I. ^d $P < 0.05$; ^e $P < 0.01$; ^f $P < 0.001$ Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on serum kidney markers of STZ diabetic rats

The STZ-diabetic rats showed a significant ($P < 0.001$) increased level of serum creatinine, BUN and decreased level of serum albumin levels as compared to the normal control group, which

indicated a significant alternation in the kidney function of diabetic rats, After treatment with APLE the creatinine content and BUN content was decreased and serum albumin level was dose dependently increased in STZ induced diabetic rats. The treatment of APLE 400 mg/kg showed significant ($P<0.001$) reversal action on kidney function of diabetic rats (Table 5).

Table 5: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on serum kidney markers of STZ diabetic rats

Treatment	Creatinine (mg/dl)	BUN (mg/dl)	Albumin (gm %)
Group-I (Normal Control)	0.90 ± 0.01	16.45 ± 0.33	7.20 ± 0.12
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	1.52 ± 0.02 ^c	35.00 ± 0.37 ^c	2.33 ± 0.43 ^c
Group-III (Metformin -200 mg/kg)	1.07 ± 0.01 ^c	23.87 ± 0.42 ^a	2.67 ± 0.05 ^c
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	0.97 ± 0.03 ^f	21.09 ± 0.21 ^d	4.78 ± 0.03 ^{bc}
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	0.89 ± 0.01 ^f	17.02 ± 0.09 ^f	6.45 ± 0.10 ^f

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^a $P<0.05$; ^b $P<0.01$; ^c $P<0.001$ Vs Group I. ^d $P<0.05$; ^e $P<0.01$; ^f $P<0.001$ Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on urine parameters of STZ diabetic rats

The results in table 6 showed that the urinary albumin, total protein contents were significantly ($P<0.001$) increased and urinary creatinine content was significantly decreased ($P<0.001$) in the STZ-diabetic rats, as compared to the normal control. After treatment with Metformin, APLE 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg the altered urinary content of creatinine, albumin and total protein contents were reversed in STZ induced diabetic rats. The treatment of APLE 400 mg/kg showed significant ($P<0.001$) reversal action on all the tested urinary parameters of diabetic rats.

Table 6: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on urine parameters of STZ diabetic rats

Treatment	Creatinine (mg/24hrs)	Albumin (g/24 hrs)	Total protein (mg/dl)
Group-I (Normal Control)	21.45± 0.22	0.08 ± 0.01	11.67 ± 0.54
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	11.23 ± 0.08 ^c	0.50 ± 0.04 ^c	29.33 ± 0.76 ^c
Group-III (Metformin -200 mg/kg)	16.56 ± 0.03 ^e	0.14 ± 0.01 ^f	18.98 ± 0.12 ^e
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	18.45 ± 0.03 ^f	0.24 ± 0.06 ^{bc}	17.27 ± 0.33 ^f
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	20.89 ± 0.02 ^f	0.13 ± 0.02 ^f	15.32 ± 0.43 ^f

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^d P<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on kidney fraction weight of STZ diabetic rats

Animals were sacrificed further to study and kidney fractional weight was measured. The kidney fraction weight was significantly (P<0.05) higher in the diabetic control rats as compared to the normal control. When compared to the disease control the Kidney fractional weight decreased in Metformin, APLE 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg, the resultant KFW reduction was significant in the high-dose of APLE treated groups. The results are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on kidney fraction weight of STZ diabetic rats

Treatment	Kidney Fraction Weight (in gm)
Group-I (Normal Control)	1.60 ± 0.04
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	2.68 ± 0.09 ^a
Group-III (Metformin -200 mg/kg)	1.90 ± 0.01
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	2.06 ± 0.02
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	1.78 ± 0.04 ^d

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as ^aP<0.05; ^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^d P<0.05; ^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on antioxidant parameters of STZ diabetic rats

The significantly (P<0.001) higher levels of Malondialdehyde (MDA) (a marker of lipid peroxidation) were detected in the kidney of diabetic rats. SOD, CAT and GSH activities were significantly (P<0.001) decreased in the kidney of STZ-diabetic rats as compared to the normal control rats. In comparison between the treatments APLE at the dose of 200 and 400 mg/kg significantly decreased the increased level of MDA and significantly increased the decreased activities of SOD and GSH. The treatment of APLE at the dose of 400 mg/kg showed significant reversal action on the STZ induced oxidative stress changes in the diabetic rats (Table 8).

Table 8: Effect of *A. pennata* ethanolic leaves extract on antioxidant parameters of STZ diabetic rats

Treatment	MDA (nmol/100 g protein)	SOD (Units/ 100 g protein)	GSH Px (μ g/ 100 g protein)	Catalase (Units/ 100 g protein)
Group-I (Normal Control)	4.78 \pm 0.44	4.89 \pm 0.07	17.10 \pm 0.43	10.00 \pm 0.21
Group-II (Diabetic Control)	12.70 \pm 0.16 ^c	1.25 \pm 0.12 ^c	6.33 \pm 0.32 ^c	4.30 \pm 0.33 ^c
Group-III (Metformin -200 mg/kg)	10.67 \pm 0.31 ^b	2.33 \pm 0.04 ^c	10.25 \pm 0.12 ^{ad}	5.30 \pm 0.22 ^b
Group-IV (APLE-200 mg/kg)	6.23 \pm 0.10 ^f	3.80 \pm 0.23 ^e	14.06 \pm 0.67 ^f	7.80 \pm 0.12 ^e
Group-V (APLE-400 mg/kg)	5.15 \pm 0.08 ^f	4.76 \pm 0.09 ^f	15.43 \pm 0.20 ^f	9.20 \pm 0.02 ^f

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, N=6, Statistical significance represented as^aP<0.05;^bP<0.01; ^cP<0.001 Vs Group I. ^d P<0.05;^eP<0.01; ^fP<0.001 Vs Group II. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc multiple comparison tests

Histopathological Changes

The control rats and the treatments showed normal histological structure of pancreas islet of Langerhans cells. But the STZ induced diabetic rats showed degenerated islet of Langerhans cells with infiltration of inflammatory cells, also moderate infiltration was observed in the Metformin and APLE 200 mg/kg treatments, almost complete recovery was observed in the high dose of 400 mg/kg APLE treatment (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Histopathology of Pancreas (Hematoxylin and Eosin staining under a light microscope at 40x magnification). A: Control rats; B: STZ-diabetic rats; C: Metformin 100 mg/kg treated group; D: APLE 200 mg/kg treated group; E: APLE 400 mg/kg treated group. IL- Islet of Langerhans.

Control rats did not show any abnormal morphological changes in H&E stained kidney specimens. Normal architecture and glomerular size and basement membrane thickness were

observed in control rats. The kidney specimens of STZ-diabetic rats, moderate to severe vacuolar degeneration of tubules and increased glomerular space was observed. APLE significantly reduced vacuolar degeneration of tubules at 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg dose levels but failed to demonstrate the same at Metformin 200 mg/kg treatment (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Histopathology of kidney (Hematoxylin and Eosin staining under a light microscope at 40x magnification). A: Control rats; B: STZ-diabetic rats; C: Metformin 100 mg/kg treated group; D: APLE 200 mg/kg treated group; E: APLE 400 mg/kg treated group. G: Glomeruli, GS: Glomerular space, VD: Vacuolar degeneration.

Discussion

Diabetic nephropathy (DN) remains one of the most serious microvascular complications of diabetes, contributing significantly to morbidity and progression to end-stage renal disease [3]. Despite current therapeutic options, complete prevention or reversal of DN is still limited. In this context, plant-derived bioactive compounds have gained attention for their multitargeted protective effects. The present study investigated the efficacy of *Acacia pennata* ethanolic leaf extract (APLE) in STZ-induced diabetic nephropathy, and the following discussion integrates the study findings with previous research and mechanistic insights.

The primary phytochemical analysis of *A. pennata* leaves extract showed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, steroids, glycosides, proteins, tannins, phenols, terpenes & sterols. The quantitative estimation of *A. pennata* leaves ethanolic extract showed the rich content of total flavonoids 52.15 mg/g, followed by total phenolic content 45.00 mg/g, and total alkaloid content of 23.35 mg/g.

The safety of the *A. pennata* leaves ethanolic extract was evaluated by acute oral toxicity study as per OECD guideline 423. The APLE did not show any toxic symptoms or mortality at the limit dose of 2000 mg/kg p.o., which showed that the APLE is safe to use up to 2000 mg/kg. STZ administration caused persistent hyperglycemia in diabetic control rats, consistent with previous reports where STZ induces β -cell necrosis leading to insulin deficiency. Persistent hyperglycemia is a central pathogenic driver of DN, leading to metabolic and hemodynamic derangements that progressively damage the kidney [17, 18]. In the present study, diabetic rats developed marked hyperglycemia following STZ injection, consistent with STZ's β -cell cytotoxicity and resultant insulin deficiency [18]. APLE administration significantly reduced fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels in a dose-dependent manner. The effect is likely mediated through the synergistic action of flavonoids, phenolics, and tannins, which modulate insulin secretion, glucose uptake, and carbohydrate metabolism.

Diabetes is often accompanied by dyslipidemia, which exacerbates renal injury through lipotoxicity, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction [19]. In the current study, diabetic rats exhibited increased serum triglycerides, LDL, and total cholesterol, with decreased HDL. These alterations are consistent with the metabolic profile of diabetic nephropathy [20]. APLE

treatment restored lipid balance by lowering triglycerides, LDL, and total cholesterol while raising HDL levels. This effect parallels earlier reports where flavonoid-rich extracts improved lipid metabolism in experimental diabetes [19, 20].

Diabetic nephropathy is clinically characterized by elevated serum creatinine, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), and reduced serum albumin [21]. In this study, diabetic control rats exhibited all these hallmarks, reflecting impaired glomerular filtration and renal injury. Treatment with APLE significantly improved renal function markers, lowering creatinine and BUN while increasing serum albumin. These findings are consistent with previous reports where plant polyphenols preserved renal function by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation [22, 23].

Proteinuria and albuminuria are key predictors of DN progression [21]. In this study, diabetic rats exhibited marked albuminuria and proteinuria, while APLE-treated rats showed significant reductions in urinary protein and albumin excretion. These results suggest that APLE preserved glomerular filtration barrier integrity, particularly podocyte function. This is supported by earlier findings that flavonoids protect podocytes from hyperglycemia-induced injury by reducing oxidative stress and stabilizing cytoskeletal proteins [24].

Oxidative stress plays a central role in DN progression, with excessive ROS generation overwhelming endogenous antioxidant systems [25]. In this study, diabetic rats exhibited elevated lipid peroxidation (MDA levels) and depleted renal antioxidant enzymes (SOD, CAT, GSH). APLE treatment restored antioxidant enzyme levels and reduced MDA concentrations. This confirms the potent free radical scavenging activity of *A. pennata*, attributed to flavonoids and phenolic compounds [26]. The antioxidant defense provided by APLE is comparable to other polyphenolic agents such as resveratrol and curcumin, which reduce ROS-mediated renal injury in diabetic models [27].

Histological examination revealed glomerulosclerosis, mesangial expansion, and tubular degeneration in diabetic control rats. These features align with the established pathology of DN [28, 29]. Conversely, APLE-treated rats showed preserved glomerular architecture, reduced mesangial expansion, and near-normal renal histology. Thus, APLE not only corrected biochemical parameters but also conferred structural renoprotection.

The observed renoprotective effects of APLE can be attributed to its rich phytochemical composition, particularly flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which exert antihyperglycemic, antihyperlipidemic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activities. These findings are consistent with earlier studies on *A. pennata* and related polyphenol-rich medicinal plants that demonstrate multitargeted protective effects in diabetic complications.

In conclusion, APLE demonstrated significant nephroprotective activity in STZ-induced diabetic rats by mitigating hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, and renal dysfunction. The extract's multitargeted mechanism of action supports its therapeutic potential as a complementary or alternative approach for managing diabetic nephropathy. However, further studies are required to isolate and characterize its active phytoconstituents, evaluate long-term safety and efficacy, and confirm its clinical applicability in human diabetic populations.

References

1. Hossain MJ, Al-Mamun M, Islam MR. Diabetes mellitus, the fastest growing global public health concern: Early detection should be focused. *Health Sci Rep.* 2024;7(3):e2004.
2. Lu Y, Wang W, Liu J, Xie M, Liu Q, Li S. Vascular complications of diabetes: A narrative review. *Medicine (Baltimore).* 2023;102(40):e35285.
3. Lim AKh. Diabetic nephropathy - complications and treatment. *Int J Nephrol Renovasc Dis.* 2014;7:361-81.
4. Ahmad J. Management of diabetic nephropathy: recent progress and future perspective. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews.* 2015;9(4):343-58.
5. Tangvarasittichai S. Oxidative stress, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia and type 2 diabetes mellitus. *World J Diabetes.* 2015;6(3):456-80.
6. Bhatti JS, Sehrawat A, Mishra J, Sidhu IS, Navik U, Khullar N, Kumar S, Bhatti GK, Reddy PH. Oxidative stress in the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes and related complications: Current therapeutics strategies and future perspectives. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine.* 2022;184:114-34.
7. Jha R, Lopez-Trevino S, Kankanamalage HR, Jha JC. Diabetes and renal complications: an overview on pathophysiology, biomarkers and therapeutic interventions. *Biomedicines.* 2024;12(5):1098.
8. Tungmunnithum D, Thongboonyou A, Pholboon A, Yangsabai A. Flavonoids and Other Phenolic Compounds from Medicinal Plants for Pharmaceutical and Medical Aspects: An Overview. *Medicines (Basel).* 2018;5(3):93.
9. Nethengwe M, Kerebba N, Okaiyeto K, Opuwari CS, Oguntibeju OO. Phenolic compounds profile and hypoglycaemic, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties of aqueous leaf extract of *Androstachys johnsonii* Prain: *In vitro* study. *South African Journal of Botany.* 2025;180:668-79.
10. Zothantluanga JH, Bhat HR, Shakya A. A systematic review on the nutraceutical potential of *Acacia pennata* (L.) Willd. *Curr. Trends Pharm. Res.* 2019;6:12-27.
11. Dongmo AB, Miyamoto T, Yoshikawa K, Arihara S, Lacaille-Dubois MA. Flavonoids from *Acacia pennata* and their cyclooxygenase (COX-1 and COX-2) inhibitory activities. *Planta medica.* 2007;73(11):1202-7.

12. Kokate CK, Purohit PA, Gokhale SB. Pharmacognosy-techniques and experiments. Pune: Nirali Prakashan. 2010; 1(3):1-33.
13. Shalini K, Ilango K. Preliminary Phytochemical Studies, GC-MS Analysis and In vitro Antioxidant Activity of Selected Medicinal Plants and its Polyherbal Formulation. Pharmacog J. 2021;13(3): 648-59.
14. Garg P, Garg R. Phytochemical screening and quantitative estimation of total flavonoids of *Ocimum sanctum* in different solvent extract. Pharma Innov. 2019; 8(2);16-21.
15. Madaan R, Bansal G, Kumar S, Sharma A. Estimation of total phenols and flavonoids in extracts of *Actaea spicata* roots and antioxidant activity studies. Indian J Pharm Sci 2011;73:666-9.
16. OECD O. Guideline for the Testing of Chemicals. Acute Oral Toxicity e Acute Toxic Class Method: Test No-423. Organ Econ Coop Dev. 2001.
17. Alaofi AL. Sinapic acid ameliorates the progression of streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic nephropathy in rats via NRF2/HO-1 mediated pathways. Frontiers in Pharmacology. 2020;11:1119.
18. Novelli M, Bonamassa B, Masini M, Funel N, Canistro D, De Tata V, Martano M, Soleti A, Campani D, Paolini M, Masiello P. Persistent correction of hyperglycemia in streptozotocin-nicotinamide-induced diabetic mice by a non-conventional radical scavenger. Naunyn Schmiedebergs Arch Pharmacol. 2010;382(2):127-37.
19. Chae SY, Kim Y, Park CW. Oxidative Stress Induced by Lipotoxicity and Renal Hypoxia in Diabetic Kidney Disease and Possible Therapeutic Interventions: Targeting the Lipid Metabolism and Hypoxia. Antioxidants (Basel). 2023;12(12):2083.
20. Xie P, Xie W, Wang Z, Guo Z, Tang R, Yang H, Wei Y, Zhou L, Huang Y, Zhao L, Zhang L. Association of diabetic nephropathy with lipid metabolism: a Mendelian randomization study. Diabetol Metab Syndr. 2025;17(1):102.
21. Dabla PK. Renal function in diabetic nephropathy. World J Diabetes. 2010;1(2):48-56.
22. Krawczyk M, Burzynska-Pedziwiatr I, Wozniak LA, Bukowiecka-Matusiak M. Impact of Polyphenols on Inflammatory and Oxidative Stress Factors in Diabetes Mellitus: Nutritional Antioxidants and Their Application in Improving Antidiabetic Therapy. Biomolecules. 2023;13(9):1402.

23. Alabi QK, Akomolafe RO, Omole JG, Aturamu A, Ige MS, Kayode OO, Kajewole-Alabi D. Polyphenol-rich extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves prevented toxic effects of cyclophosphamide on the kidney function of Wistar rats. *BMC Complement Med Ther.* 2021;21(1):274.
24. Gong L, Wang R, Wang X, Liu J, Han Z, Li Q, Jin Y, Liao H. Research progress of natural active compounds on improving podocyte function to reduce proteinuria in diabetic kidney disease. *Ren Fail.* 2023;45(2):2290930.
25. Bhatti JS, Sehrawat A, Mishra J, Sidhu IS, Navik U, Khullar N, Kumar S, Bhatti GK, Reddy PH. Oxidative stress in the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes and related complications: Current therapeutics strategies and future perspectives. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine.* 2022;184:114-34.
26. Zothantluanga JH, Bhat HR, Shakya A. A systematic review on the nutraceutical potential of *Acacia pennata* (L.) Willd. *Curr. Trends Pharm. Res.* 2019;6:12-27.
27. Wang CY, Wu DL, Yu MH, Wang CY, Liang HW, Lee HJ. Apple Polyphenol Mitigates Diabetic Nephropathy via Attenuating Renal Dysfunction with Antioxidation in Streptozotocin-Induced Diabetic Rats. *Antioxidants (Basel).* 2025 23;14(2):130.
28. Pourghasem M, Shafi H, Babazadeh Z. Histological changes of kidney in diabetic nephropathy. *Caspian J Intern Med.* 2015 Summer;6(3):120-7.
29. Carrara C, Abbate M, Conti S, Rottoli D, Rizzo P, Marchetti G. Histological examination of the diabetic kidney. In *Diabetic Nephropathy: Methods and Protocols* 2019 Nov 8 (pp. 63-87). New York, NY: Springer US.